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Thermal requisite for seed germination in garden pea (*Pisum sativum* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Minimum temperature required for the essential physiological functions in any crop is mandatory for crop scheduling. Minimum temperature required for seed germination under field situations was studied, during peak winters under extreme cold arid deserts of Ladakh, India. A mean soil temperature of 7.25 °C over 7 consecutive days has successfully effected the seed germination. Based on these requisites, exact sowing schedules for all pea crops under open as well as greenhouse conditions were designed, which increased the cropping intensity in Ladakh by 100 % in open field and by 50 % under greenhouse conditions. The physiological influences of low temperature on garden peas, and the regressive relations among soil and atmospheric temperatures in open field as well as inside solar greenhouses are also discussed here (**Keywords:** abiotic stress, cold tolerance, frost, garden pea, physiology, temperature).

INTRODUCTION

Thorough knowledge on the climatic requisite of any plant species is the prime requisite for its successful domestication, Peas being a short duration crop, follow up of the exact planting season lead by the clear cut knowledge on the thermal requisites for essential physiological functions could enhance the cropping intensity and hence the economic returns (Chauhan and Mangal, 1993). Usually, the minimal thermal requisites are understood by mechanically simulating the low temperature conditions under the laboratory situations. The process will be very time consuming and laborious, since only one temperature profile could be possible at a time. Thus, the treatment combinations make the study extremely intricate and often force to approximations. The alternate will be to conduct the experiment in real time, under such a field condition, for which the availability of suitable field, wherein the cultivation is attempted with greenhouse even at freezing temperatures outside will be the major lacuna. Ladakh is at an altitude of 11500 ft above mean sea level (MSL) in the trans-Himalayan zone of India. It has extreme cold arid desert climate and its cropping season is restricted to first week of May to second week of September and thus, quite unique agriculturally. These climatic specialties make Ladakh the ideal point for experimentation on minimal thermal requisites of peas. In this region, a maximum of two crops of garden peas is possible in a year, under greenhouse conditions with the

first crop being sown in second week of March and second crop in the first week of July and to complete in second week of October (Singh, 1995). The usual open field practice is single crop from first week of June to second week of September. Pea being a 105 days crop with cultivated varieties (including Bonneville which is under study) come to flowering in 55 - 60 days (Veeraragavathatham *et al.*, 1994) and any efficient strategy to extend the cropping season by 45 days on both sides of the maximum duration will result in higher cropping intensity. Since, temperature being the only known factor restricting the cropping in off-season and lack of knowledge on the minimal requirement for garden pea, (Chauhan and Mangal, 1993), an experiment was laid during the peak winters of 2005 and 2006 in Ladakh.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiments were conducted at Field Research Laboratory, Defence Research and Development Organization, India, at an altitude of 11500 ft above MSL. This trans-Himalayan zone is designated as cold-arid region with the night temperatures generally remaining below zero degrees round the year. Winter-summer transition phase of this region was ideally selected for understanding the minimal thermal requisites for germination of pea seeds. For seed germination studies, seeds were sown on 7th March 2005 and 2006 under open field conditions on soil surface and at 1.0 cm depth. For comparative studies, seeds were

also sown under zero energy cool chamber based double walled solar polyench greenhouse (Singh and Ahmed, 2005) and first irrigation was provided simultaneously for both the crops. Under both open field and polyench conditions, the experiment area was divided into 6 plots of 10 m² each and each plot was considered as replication and observation on seed germination from each replication was recorded separately. Hourly data on soil temperature fluctuation (at 2.0 cm depth) was recorded using semi-automatic meteorological instrument Datalogger (model WDL 1002, Weather Technologies) and transferred using detachable memory module and analyzed using the software Comdrv prmppt 1.1. For the seeds sown at soil-air interface (0.25 - 0.50 cm depth), the day before and for

seeds sown at 1.0 cm depth, two days before the appearance of plumule above soil was considered as the date of germination. Data on atmospheric and soil temperatures are presented in Figure 1. Standard cultural practices, as detailed by Singh *et al.* (2003) were followed in crop management and during nights, crop was further protected with a poly tunnel. Mean temperature data over specified number of previous days on the particular date is presented in Table 1. Studies on temperature required for seed germination could not be done during October last week since, the mean soil temperature inside greenhouse was higher (10.84 °C) than that required to hinder the germination and much lower in open field till March.

Table 1. Maximum, minimum and mean soil temperatures along with mean over the specific number of previous days as on date for the winter 2005, deciding the seed germination in garden pea

Date (2005)	ST max.	ST min.	ST Mean	2 d	3 d	4 d	5 d	6 d	7 d
7-Mar	12.8	-1.2	3.95						
8-Mar	15.0	-1.5	4.59	4.27					
9-Mar	10.2	-0.8	3.20	3.89	3.91				
10-Mar	15.1	-1.0	4.80	4.00	4.20	4.13			
11-Mar	16.3	-1.1	5.17	4.98	4.39	4.44	4.34		
12-Mar	18.8	-1.1	6.02	5.59	5.33	4.80	4.76	4.62	
13-Mar	21.0	-0.7	6.90	6.46	6.03	5.72	5.22	5.11	4.95
14-Mar	24.0	1.0	8.50	7.70	7.14	6.65	6.28	5.77	5.60
15-Mar	24.3	3.1	9.32	8.91	8.24	7.69	7.18	6.79	6.27
16-Mar	22.2	2.8	8.50	8.91	8.78	8.31	7.85	7.40	7.03
17-Mar	11.9	2.3	4.83	6.67	7.55	7.79	7.61	7.35	7.04
18-Mar	12.6	2.0	4.97	4.90	6.10	6.90	7.22	7.17	7.01
19-Mar	12.0	2.6	4.97	4.97	4.92	5.82	6.52	6.85	6.86
20-Mar	14.6	0.8	5.24	5.10	5.06	5.00	5.70	6.30	6.62
21-Mar	06.8	-0.2	2.24	3.74	4.15	4.35	4.45	5.12	5.72
22-Mar	13.6	-0.5	4.46	3.35	3.98	4.23	4.37	4.45	5.03
23-Mar	12.5	-0.6	4.05	4.25	3.58	4.00	4.19	4.32	4.39
24-Mar	20.1	1.9	7.48	5.77	5.33	4.56	4.69	4.74	4.77
25-Mar	20.3	0.2	6.97	7.23	6.17	5.74	5.04	5.07	5.06
26-Mar	25.6	2.3	9.49	8.23	7.98	7.00	6.49	5.78	5.70
27-Mar	18.7	0.3	6.46	7.98	7.64	7.60	6.89	6.49	5.88
28-Mar	23.8	-0.7	7.85	7.15	7.93	7.69	7.65	7.05	6.68
29-Mar	24.2	0.6	8.44	8.14	7.58	8.06	7.84	7.78	7.25

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Daily average air temperature under open field was a function of $y = 0.609156 + 0.449789X_1$ where, X_1 is the mean of maximum and minimum air temperatures. Similarly daily average soil temperature was found to be $y = 0.68 X_2$ where, X_2 was the mean of maximum and minimum daily soil temperatures. Soil temperature was a function of air temperature $(0.549453 + 1.88478X_3)$ where X_3 was the daily average air temperature under open field. Under double walled polyenych greenhouse, seed germination was observed on 14th March 2005 (7 days after sowing) showing that germination is a function of soil temperature over 7 days. Daily average air temperature under polyenych was found to be a function of $y = +1.05084X_4$ where, X_4 is the arithmetic mean of maximum and minimum temperatures; further, soil temperature under polyenych greenhouse was related to air temperature by $y = -5.75606 + 1.24895X_5$ where X_5 is daily average air temperature. Further soil temperature under polyenych greenhouse was a function of air temperature under open field ($y = 6.51282 + 1.70831X_6$ where, X_6 is the atmospheric temperature), clearly showing the high level suitability of low cost polyenych greenhouses for winter vegetable cultivation.

The date of seed germination was characterized by mean soil temperature of 9.57 °C over 7 consecutive days showing the possibility of germination at a lower temperature.

Germination of seeds sown at 1.0cm depth was observed on 29th March 2005 (23 days after sowing) and the day was characterized by a mean air and soil temperatures of 3.28 °C of 8.44 °C respectively. From Table 1, it is evident that seed germination in peas is not a response of temperature level over 2, 3, 4 or 5 consecutive days since 16th March, though with no flowering, was characterized by higher temperatures than 29th March over these periods. It was observed that neither 7.78 °C over 6 days nor 7.25 °C over 7 days have lead to the germination. Since the polyenych studies have proved that the germination is a response to 7 days temperature, it may be concluded that soil temperature of 7.25 °C or atmospheric temperature of 3.12 °C over 7 days will lead to pea seed germination. Interestingly, in carrot also, the minimum temperature required for seed germination was reported to be 7.2 °C, without mentioning the duration (Kale and Masalkar, 1993). In garden pea, due to low temperatures, a total inhibition of physiological functions including the photosynthesis

Figure 1. Air and soil temperatures under open field and inside polyenych greenhouse affecting seed germination in garden pea under Ladakh conditions

was previously reported (Streb *et al.*, 2008) and the observed requirement of minimum specific temperature is confirmatory to the same. Further, Anto and Jayaram (2010) had shown that unlike other pulses, garden pea seeds are highly sensitive to temperature and extremes may result in hard seeds. It was postulated that the pulses such as soybean escapes this situation since their seeds are rich in oil. Mitigation of high temperature induced low germination in garden pea with artificial induction of low temperatures is also reported (Shereena and Salim, 2006). The mechanism behind the lower germination below the cut-off temperature is explained to be the cold-induced drastic reduction in the gibberellins levels in the plant (Stavang *et al.*, 2007).

Seeds at soil-air interface in sandy soil had germinated on 22nd March (16 days after sowing). This day was characterized by a mean soil temperature of 5.03 °C (at 1.0 cm depth) and mean daily temperature of 3.51 °C over 7 days. Reason for the germination is obvious, since under bright sunlight the surface sandy soil may get heated up more and quicker leading to fulfillment of the thermal requisite for germination, and at 1.0 cm depth, temperature available was lower than the minimal requisite. Thus, it appears to be that seed germination is a temperature response directed by the depth of sowing and the soil type. There will be a minimum temperature difference of 2.22 °C between the soil on the surface and at 1.0 cm depth. At lower temperatures, the germination will be slow in peas (Chapman *et al.*, 1983), since it is associated with increasing cytoplasmic volume and increased activities of enzymes in the Calvin cycle and in sucrose biosynthesis pathway (Strand *et al.*, 1999).

CONCLUSION

This study paves a way for a new cropping system comprising of 3 crops under Ladakh conditions to obtain 50 % higher intensity under greenhouses and 100 % over open field. Since pea takes 60 days for flowering, under polycarbonate greenhouse conditions, the first crop should be sown in the last week of December (20th - 25th), second in the first week of April and last crop in the second week of July. First crop till second week of January and last crop after second week of September should be protected under tunnels during nights for proper flower induction and pod development

respectively. Under open field, first crop should be sown in the last week of March and the second in the first week of July to be finished in second week of October. If the first crop till April first week and second crop after September second week are protected under poly tunnels, better seed germination and pod development respectively could be realized. The fact that the development of a cold tolerant variety is highly difficult, since this character in garden peas may be a quantitative character governed by recessive genes may add to the significance of this study.

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Received March, 2013 : Accepted June, 2013